

The ANCHISE project in search of data: situation and strategies

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ANCHISE (methods, knowledge and toolkit to enhance the protection of cultural heritage against looting and illicit trafficking) is a Horizon Europe project that aims to develop a global and comprehensive response to the challenges of effective protection of cultural heritage in Europe, in order to provide sustainable and replicable solutions. By integrating new tools developed during the project, ANCHISE will bridge the gap between new technologies and end-users involved in CH protection, with effective use in operations, and will rely on a network of users and experts.

ANCHISE objectives are:

- 1) To evaluate technologies on – or close to – the market, using user-centred methods to help bridge the gap between technologies and the market (looting detection, detection of neglected or abandoned heritage, object identification and traceability, object marking).
- 2) To implement Pilot Experimentation Areas to understand local, sociological and economic contexts, mobilize local stakeholders, train beta-users, specify and implement technology demonstrations, evaluate the impact of replicability of demonstrations.
- 3) To develop imagery, SFS and 3D recognition to improve the documentation and recording of objects, then control the provenance of objects and detect illicit trafficking.
- 4) To disseminate the results of the project, engage and increase the capacity of communities to help bridge the gap between innovation and LEAs, museums, archaeologists, art dealers, auction houses and citizens.

As part of ANCHISE, the members of the international consortium are therefore developing a number of technological tools that will be able to help local players involved in the fight against looting and illegal trafficking. That's why ANCHISE members are looking back at the dilemmas and difficulties described in the round table presentation, and the coordinators would be delighted to present the strategy for dealing with, for example, the following questions:

How can we create partnerships with the public and private institutions we approach to request access to their databases in order to train the artificial intelligence and software of our technological tools?

What best practices or ideas can we implement concerning IP management and the sustainability of tools and partnerships with institutions after the end of our projects?